

Socio-Economic Conditions of Marine Fishermen in Ramanathapuram District, Tamil Nadu, India

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Abstract : India is one of the top ten fish producing countries in the world in terms of production and export of sea food. Fishing is considered to be a strong source of income and employment. The sector has made a substantial contribution to foreign exchange. The present paper appraised the Socio-economic positions of marine fishermen of Rameswaram in Ramanathapuram District. In the present study, both quantifiable and categorical data were collected by virtue of interview schedule and analyzed by using statistical tools like; Chi-square test, Ranking scales and Factor analysis. The analysis signifies the socio-economic status of marine fishermen, problems faced and important factors which determines their standard of living, expectation of benefits from the Government. Chi-square test betrays income status, savings culture, duration of fishing, consumption habits of the respondents. Ranking scales patrons the expectation of benefits from the Government and the Factor analysis designate the problems on marketing of fishes & the factors influencing the level of satisfaction of marine fishermen towards their occupation. The study concludes that the fishermen are in generally poor, semiliterate, illiterate; poor family income, gargantuan associated with destitute financial inputs have left many of the fishermen in an impoverished economic status. Further the proper marketing and storage facilities for the yield is need of the hour. The suggestions of these findings and the significance of the study are discussed and the outcomes of the present research useful for the Policy Makers.

Keywords : Fisheries, Social-Economic Status, Occupational Status and Livelihood of Fishermen, Ramanathapuram District, Tamil Nadu.

Personal Reflexive Statement

India is a country with people from various backgrounds and occupations. Several communities are based out of the occupations that people perform, and thereby their socio-economic conditions differ drastically from one another. For this reason, it is important to analyze and understand the lives and socio-economic conditions of people in communities to determine their standard of living and improve upon them. In this context, the present research paper is an strive to determine the socio-economic status of the marine fishermen in Ramanathapuram district, Tamil Nadu. It is well known that the fishermen community faces various challenges in meeting their basic needs due to various factors like changes in climatic conditions, environment protection standards, and declining sea life. Therefore, an effort has been taken to study the socio-economic condition of the fishermen in Rameswaram, Ramanathapuram District. It is one of the most popular coastal districts of Tamil Nadu – Ramanathapuram. The researcher believes that the findings of the study would not only help to derive an unbiased analysis of the livelihood of the people in the community, but also helps in developing the future course of actions to be undertaken to uplift them.

Introduction

India is considered as third largest fish producer in the world with 14.75 million tonnes of fish produced in the year 2023. The total value of marine product exports from India was \$4.54 billion in the fiscal year 2021-2022. This sector has made a substantial contribution to foreign exchange earnings which stand at fiscal year 2022-2023, frozen shrimp alone earned \$5.48 billion and 1.36 million metric tonnes of seafood in the year 2022-2023 and the earnings amount to 1.24 percent of the GDP. In India, around 4 million fishermen with approximately 61% living below the poverty line and depend on fisheries for their bread and butter. Those directly involved in fishing activities as well as engaged in allied activities such as fish processing, marketing, and net making. Besides, fisheries sector provides livelihood, employment and entrepreneurship to fishing folk. It is axiomatic that for enhancing food, security, alleviating poverty and generating further employment opportunities are a must. India has a long coastline of 8,118 Km with an Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), which is highly appropriate for capture and culture fisheries. India's marine fish marketing has changed quickly over the years. Fish and fisheries products are becoming more and more popular worldwide due to their high nutritional content. The intensity of fishing increased with the demand for fish, and target fishing in open access fisheries resulted

from an overabundance of some types. Tamil Nadu has emerged as a leading maritime fish producer, with an yearly production of 929.000 tons in 2023. Ramanathapuram district is the main producer of marine fish in the State, followed by Nagapattinam, Thiruvarur and Thanjavur, Tuticorin, Kanniyakumari, and Chennai put together reckoned for over 60% of the state's marine fish production. Despite this, fishermen tend to be low-income individuals with low literacy rates, low family incomes, and few opportunities for other employment. Numerous specialized programs and initiatives have been consistently introduced by the Central and State governments. Within this framework, the current study concentrated on issues that are now pertinent to the general improvement of fisherman in general and the Rameshwarm fishermen in Ramanathapuram District specifically.

Review of Literature

The following reviews have been used by the researcher to support the study problem that was chosen.

Selvaraj. N (2022) has stated in his research "Socio-Economic Conditions of the Fishermen in Tamil Nadu – India" that the market for marine products of the nation in Asia has not well organized. He proposed that the markets need to be reformed by bringing in new management approaches and updating the standard fish selling tactics.

S. Manimaran & Dr. K. Suriyan, (2021), conducted "A Study on Socio-Economic Condition on Fishermen in Cuddalore District" and concluded that, Their standard of living is going to get better. However, extremely low incomes increase the likelihood of starving, pose problems for their children's education, and result in a bad quality of living that inevitably leads to a terrible social life, all of which have a detrimental effect on the individual's life. Price increases for food, essential services, medical care, and education.

Emaldarani. S & Dr.A.Kanmani Joan (2019) have concluded in their research paper as "Socio-Economic Status of Fishermen Community (with special reference to Nagapattinam Town, Tamil Nadu)". The fishermen's economic situation was so dire that they weren't even entirely focused on fishing. The minimum requirements were not met by the maximum number of fisherman. The majority of fishermen showed little awareness of contemporary capture fishing methods.

Vivek Parashar, Satish Kumar Bara, Dinesh Damde, Ankit Kumar and Vipin Vyas (2016), in their research "Assessment of the socio-economic status of

fishermen communities: a case study from a selected reach of River Narmada, India" observed that, A Significant parts of the riverine capture fishery industry are the traditional fishing communities. The study suggested that, by raising capture rates, fisheries regulations can both protect the natural biodiversity and enhance the standard of living for fishermen. Daily fish marketing should be conducted in order to sustain the fundamental necessities of the current rural communities. In the off-season for fishing, ventures such as beekeeping, gardening, handicrafts, etc., should be launched to generate revenue.

Bijayalakshmi Devi and, Ajit Kumar (2014), in their study came to the conclusion, that a wide range of studies on the socioeconomic conditions in the area have been used to construct the general socioeconomic situation of fishermen in India. It is recommended that scientists and policy makers concentrate more on the establishment of backward and forward linkages on the overall socio-economic and cultural development of the fishermen.

Vhankade (2011), in his study revealed that the government provides financial support to cooperative societies through loans and subsidies to the fishing community. He suggested that, the fishermen cooperative society shall provide services and credit to the poor fishermen for working capital requirements also.

Durairaj (2009) in his study on "Marine Fishing Industry in Ramanathapuram district" focused on the distribution of revenue, debt, and the yearly average return per craft of both mechanized and non-mechanized industries, including fishery, in the Ramanathapuram district.

Ganesh Kumar et al., (2008) has conducted an in-depth study in all the major coastal states and selected inland states to understand the domestic marketing of fish in India. It has been discovered that the infrastructure at wholesale and retail markets, as well as fishing harbors, is woefully inadequate and badly maintained. The researcher strongly suggests that a unified market strategy be developed for the promotion of fish and fish products.

Ragupathy & Venkatachalam (2005) have presented a paper which looked at the threat to India's large fisheries, especially those around the Gulf of Mannar region. It is widely quoted that, many people have stated that the introduction of trawler fishing methods, which scrape the sea floor and ultimately catch young fish, is to blame for the depletion. It was advised to assess this method's efficacy critically and offer a substitute for maintaining the resources.

Shiyani, R.L, (2002) has made an examination of Rameswaram's marine fisheries' growth and instability by species and district. While Rameswaram had a sharp fall in marine fish productivity, the state's overall marine fish production increased over time. To maintain socioeconomic equilibrium, the government should take the appropriate actions to enforce maritime rules that define distinct fishing grounds for various vessel gear combinations.

Balasubramaniyan (2001) in his study, the economic standing of fishermen in two coastal fishing communities in Thoothukudi District is compared in this study. The findings show that, in both villages, the fishermen had a positive view on the motorization of fishing vessels.

Dibakar Naik (2001) have conducted a research on the patterns of marine fish landings and marketing in various Thoothukudi marine areas. In Thoothukudi, the marketing of marine fish has been handled by a multitude of middlemen who have established an extensive network of market channels.

Islam, M.S (2000) conducted a research on "Socio-economic profile in Fisheries Development" and observed that a large number of women involved in fisheries activities (such as fish collection, fish drying and net making) earned a small amount of income. The study recommended that the government and NGOs should come forward to facilitate women to be employed in income generating activities.

Verduijin (2000) carried out a survey in the Kanyakumari district on behalf of the BOBP to ascertain the basic needs of 39 coastal fishing communities. The survey's findings indicated that the use of motorization and mechanization in fishing crafts, the rise in the population of active fishermen, and the absence of alternative income-generating opportunities have all contributed to the increased intensity of fishing. The report also emphasizes how the lack of amenities for sanitary conditions, health care, and safe drinking water exacerbates the worries of the fishermen.

Statement of the Problem

India is among the nations where a sizable portion of the land is submerged beneath the sea. Because of this, the majority of people living in these areas are exclusively involved in fish farming and fishing. The socio-economic status of these people largely depends on the income from this occupation only. The

amount of fish available varies seasonally; the mechanized boats have replaced the country boats for fishing activities. There is always a relationship between the quantity of fish caught and its price. In the rainy season, the fishermen rarely enter the sea for fishing and even if they go they catch only minimum quantity which fetches them low income from these operations and at times they face financial crises. In order to meet these crises, the fishermen mortgage their valuables including gold ornaments and sometimes they draw near money lenders for getting loans at exorbitant interest. Family size combined with limited financial inputs has created many issues for the fishermen, who have low literacy rates, low family incomes, and few opportunities to transition to other jobs. Even with their moderate incomes, the fishing community is economically weak. They struggle to provide for their family in part due to their inconsistent income and in part to their alcohol addiction. So it is but natural they remain poor and always in need. Since fishing is their primary source of income, it is exceedingly difficult for them to increase their earnings and raise their family's standard of living. The current study intends to investigate the socio-economic circumstances of the fishermen in the Ramanathapuram District in this regard.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the major objectives of the study :

1. To examine the socio-economic conditions of marine fishermen of Rameswaram in Ramanathapuram District.
2. To investigate the problems faced and support provided by the Government of Tamil Nadu to boost the Socio-economic conditions of marine fishermen.
3. To present suitable suggestions based on findings.

Methodology of the Study

Sociological interest has always been piqued by studies of socioeconomic situations. The current study is focused on the socioeconomic conditions of marine fishermen.

The primary objective of the study is to comprehend the socio-economic status of marine fishermen because fisheries are the booming/flourishing sectors, which contributes considerable income on country's GDP. GDP can determine the economic development of the Country. The study has been conducted in

Rameswaram Taluk in Ramanathapuram District. The State of Tamil Nadu's Ramanathapuram District is the leading district for producing marine fish, followed by Nagapattinam, Thiruvarur, Tuticorin, Kanyakumari, and Chennai. There are nine taluks in the district: Mangadu, Akkalmadam, Anthoniatpattinam, Aiyankundu, China Palam, Mandapam, Pamban, and Thangachimadamas. A significant number of families who are fisherman live in these taluks. The researcher used a non-random sample technique (judgment sampling technique) to choose 150 marine fishermen as responders. Interview schedules were utilized to gather information about the profile of occupational activities and socioeconomic conditions. Secondary data are also collected and compiled from Books, Journals, Magazines, Publications, and Websites. The researcher used statistical methods, such as percentage analysis, weighted average ranking, Garret's ranking approach, factor analysis, and Chi-square test, to examine the data that was gathered.

Hypotheses

The researcher has established the following hypothesis in order to conduct the research :

1. The ownership of a fishing boat and monthly income are not significantly correlated.
2. The respondents' age and the amount of time they spend fishing in a year do not significantly correlate.
3. There is no discernible connection between their monthly income and their consumption patterns.

Analysis and Interpretation

Profile of Demographic Factor

When the respondents' demographic profile is examined, it becomes clear that 36% of them were primarily between the ages of 30 and 40. Most of the respondents (71.33 percent) are illiterate. A vast majority of 81.33 percent of the respondents got married, 56.67 percent live in nuclear families and 61.01 percent have more than four family members in their family belonging to the religion of Hindu followed by Christian and Muslim. Table-1 depicts the profile of demographics.

Table-1 : Demographic Profile

Demographic Factors		No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	150	100.00
	Female	0	0.00
Age	Below 20 years	17	11.33
	20-30 years	42	28.00
	30-40 years	54	36.00
	40 and above	37	24.67
Educational Qualification	No schooling	107	71.33
	Elementary	23	15.34
	Higher secondary	15	10.00
	Graduation	05	3.33
Marital Status	Single	28	18.67
	Married	122	81.33
Type of Family	Joint	65	43.33
	Nuclear	85	56.67
Size of Family	1-3	28	19.66
	4-6	92	61.01
	above 6	30	19.33
Religion	Hindu	101	67.33
	Muslim	20	13.33
	Christian	29	19.34
Occupation	Fishing	150	100.00

Source: Primary Data.

Occupational Profile

Occupation is the important source of income to the livelihood of an individual. The occupational profile of the respondents are analyzed which indicates that the majority 71.33 percent of the respondent have chosen fishing as their occupation by heredity at the age of 13-14 years. 41.33 percent of the respondents go to sea for fishing for 200-250 days a year. The majority of 42.67 percent of the respondents used country boats for fishing and 42.67 percent of the respondents were actively involved in other activities like boat repairing, training to new learners and fish vending. Only 13.33 percent of the respondents' spouses are involved in fish vending and processing work to generate income for their families. The above fact presented in Table-2.

Table-2 : Occupational Profile

Occupational Profile		No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Occupation	Fishing	150	100.00
Reasons for choosing the occupation	Hereditary	107	71.33
	Profitability	18	12.00
	Lack of alternate employment	21	14.00
	Due to interest	04	2.67
Age at the time of entry into fishing (in a year)	10 - 12	36	24.00
	13 - 14	43	28.67
	15 - 17	32	21.33
	18 - 20	27	18.00
	20 and above	12	8.00
Duration of fishing in a year (days in a year)	Less than 100	04	2.67
	100 - 150	13	8.67
	150 - 200	22	14.67
	200 - 250	62	41.33
	250 - 300	37	24.66
	300 and above	12	8.00
Mode of Vessel for Fishing	Country boats	64	42.67
	Catamarans	09	6.00
	Motor boats	51	34.00
	Fiber boats	26	17.33
Occupational problems of fishermen	Yes	114	76.00
	No	36	24.00
Work other than fishing	Yes	64	42.67
	No	86	57.33
Nature of other work	Preparing new fishing net	09	14.07
	Sale of fishing net	10	15.62
	Fish vending	13	20.31
	Boat repairing	14	21.88
	Training activities for new learners	18	28.12
Employment of family members	Employed	20	13.33
	Not employed	130	86.67
Nature of employment	Organized private sector	06	30.00
	Un organized private sector	12	60.00
	Employed in other state	01	5.00
	Employed in gulf countries	01	5.00
Occupation of spouse	Home maker	80	64.52
	Fish Vendor	31	25.00
	Processing Worker	04	3.22
	Private Employee	03	2.42
	Self-Employed	06	4.84

Source : Primary Data.

Occupational Problems of Fishermen

The researcher used the weighted average ranking method to determine the occupational problems faced by the respondents in Ramanathapuram District. The points were assigned to each variable as 7,6,5,4,3,2,1 and the total score and mean score were calculated based on which the ranks are assigned. Out of the several variables, scarcity and high net cost are assigned the highest rank, followed by inaccessibility to credit and high boat maintenance costs. These are the major problems that marine fishermen face. Table-3 displays the occupational problems of the respondents.

Table-3 : Mean Score of Occupational Problems of Fishermen

S.No.	Problems	Total Score	Mean Score	Rank
1	Scarcity and high cost of Net	257	4.50	I
2	Inaccessibility to Credit	252	4.42	II
3	High cost of Maintenance of Boats	232	4.07	III
4	Non availability of spare parts for Boats	231	4.05	IV
5	High Cost of Equipment	217	3.80	V
6	Climate Conditions	216	3.78	VI
7	Inadequate Technology	191	3.35	VII

Source : Primary Data.

Profile of Economic Status

Earnings determine the respondents' socio-economic empowerment. Income is the primary factor that allows people to live happy lives. The study shows that 54% of respondents have an income between Rs. 5,000 and Rs. 10,000. It also determines the family's spending and saving patterns. The majority of 56.67 percent of the respondents spent their whole income on food only because of the larger size of the family and 51.33 percent of the respondents save meager amounts for their future contingencies in the Post office, Commercial banks and Chit funds. The results are shown in Table-4.

Table-4 : Economic Status of the Respondents

Economic Status		No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Monthly Income (in Rs.)	Less than 5000	27	18.00
	5000- 10000	81	54.00
	10000- 15000	35	23.33
	15000 and above	07	4.67
Allocation of Income	Food only	85	56.67
	Food and Savings	39	26.00
	Fulfill all needs	26	17.33
Savings	Yes	77	51.33
	No	73	48.67
Financial Institution for Savings	Commercial Banks	08	10.38
	Co-operative Banks	06	7.80
	Post Office	30	38.96
	Private Banks	26	33.76
	Chit Fund	07	9.10

Source : Primary Data.

Expenditure Pattern

Income is an important aspect that dictates the expenditure habits of the respondents. It also determines the socio-economic situations of fishermen. The current research illustrates that the majority of 62 percent of the respondents spent above Rs.15,000 for food and clothes, followed by medical expenses 45 percent of them spent below Rs.5000, 63.33 percent of them allocate less than Rs.5,000 for their children's education. The study indicates that the expenditure on fishing, 48.67 percent of them spent in the range of Rs.50,000-75,000 towards diesel & oil for boats in a year, followed by labour charges as 36.67 percent of them spent Rs.75,000-1, 00,000 and 32 percent of the respondents spent Rs.50,000-75,000 for maintenance of boats. Table-5 discloses the fact.

The Chi-Square test was used to test the following hypotheses at a 5% level of significance in order to determine the degree of agreement between respondents' satisfaction and socioeconomic characteristics.

Table-5 : Expenditure Pattern of the Respondents

Expenditure Pattern (Rs. in a year)		No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Food and Clothing	5000-10,000	06	4.00
	10,000-15,000	51	34.00
	15,000 and above	93	62.00
Medical Expenses	Less than 5000	68	45.33
	5000-10,000	44	29.33
	10,000-15,000	35	23.33
	15,000 and above	02	1.33
Expenditure on Children's Education	Less than 5000	95	63.33
	5000-10,000	46	30.67
	10,000-15,000	09	6.00
Expenditure for festival	Less than 5000	02	1.33
	5000-10,000	48	32.00
	10,000-15,000	100	66.67
Expenses on Electricity	Less than 500	110	73.33
	500-10,00	30	20.00
	1000-1500	10	6.67
Communication Expenditure	Less than 5000	118	78.67
	5000-10,000	28	18.67
	10,000-15,000	04	2.67
Expenditure on fishing: (Rs. in a year)			
Diesel and Oil Expenditure	Less than 50,000	58	38.67
	50,000 -75,000	73	48.67
	75,000 - 1,00,000	12	8.00
	1,00,000 and above	07	4.66
Labour Charges	Less than 50,000	19	12.67
	50,000 -75,000	46	30.67
	75,000- 1,00,000	55	36.66
	1,00,000 and above	30	20.00
Maintenance Expenditure	Less than 50,000	41	27.33
	50,000- 75,000	48	32.00
	75,000- 1,00,000	39	26.00
	1,00,000 and above	22	14.67

Source : Primary Data.

H₁ : The ownership of a fishing boat and monthly income are not significantly correlated.

H₂ : The respondents' age and the amount of time they spend for fishing in a year do not significantly correlate.

H₃ : There is no discernible connection between their monthly income and their consumption patterns.

At the 5% level of significance, the calculated values for each of the aforementioned hypotheses are greater than the table value. The null hypothesis is thus disproved. As a result, there is a strong correlation between the respondents' degree of satisfaction and socioeconomic characteristics. Table-6 reveals this information.

Table-6 : Results of Chi-square Test

Between	X ²	Table Value @5% level	Inference
Ownership of boat and monthly income.	11.447	7.815	Significant
Age and duration of fishing in a year.	12.772	24.996	Insignificant
Consumption habits and monthly income.	7.866	16.919	Significant

Source : Computed Data.

(Life Style) Cultural Factors

Socioeconomic conditions speaks about lifestyle also. This study analyzed the lifestyle of fishermen in Ramanathapuram District, which indicates that most of the respondents (80 percent) owned houses like huts, concrete and tiled houses. More than 60 percent of the respondents use water from their own pumps for drinking and other purposes. The majority of 73.33 percent of them eat stable food such as rice, fish, vegetables & milk and 58 percent of the respondents spent their leisure time on watching Television. The outcomes are shown in Table-7.

Channel of Distribution in Marketing of Fish

Depending on the situation, the respondents sell their fish directly to the Consumers, Wholesaler, Retailer, and Exporter. When they sell directly it is possible for them to get a reasonable price but it is not possible always. The present study indicates that the majority of the respondents (80 percent) are forced to sell their fish to wholesalers to get immediate money and wholesalers are more benefited than fishermen. Table-8 discloses the fact.

Table-7 : (Life Style) Cultural Factors of the Respondents

Particulars		No. of Respondents		Percentage (%)
Ownership of House	Own	120		80.00
	Rented	30		20.00
Type of House	Hut	28		23.33
	Concrete house	33		27.50
	Tiled house	59		49.17
Source of drinking water	Own pump	92		61.33
	Public pump	34		22.67
	Bought from out side	12		8.00
	From neighbor	12		8.00
Source of water for cooking & other purposes	Own pump	98		65.33
	Public pump	32		21.33
	Bought from out side	12		8.00
	From neighbor	08		5.33
Source of Energy		Cooking	Lighting	Percentage (%)
	Fire wood	83	-	27.67
	Kerosene	28	16	14.67
	Gas	34	2	12.00
	Electricity	5	132	45.66
Food habits	Stable food + Fish + vegetables + milk	110		73.33
	Stable food- milk-meals+ Fish + fruits + vegetables	19		12.67
	Stable food + Fish + meat + milk + vegetables	21		14.00
Consumption Habits	Smoking	103		68.67
	Liquor	20		13.33
	Betel leaves	12		8.00
	Pan masala	15		10.00
Toilet facilities	Owned old type	54		36.00
	Common toilet	26		17.33
	Open place	70		46.67
Spending leisure time	Reading Newspaper & Magazine	25		16.67
	Watching TV	87		58.00
	Listening to Radio	04		2.67
	Playing Cricket	05		3.33
	Playing Cards	24		16.00
	Playing Dice	03		2.00
	Playing Carom	02		1.33

Source : Primary Data.

Table-8 : Profile of Marketing of Fishes

Profile of Marketing		No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Marketing Channel	To Consumers	06	04.00
	To Wholesellers	120	80.00
	To Retailers	21	14.00
	To Exporters	03	02.00
Beneficiaries on Marketing	Local Agents	06	04.00
	Exporters	03	02.00
	Whole Sellers	124	82.67
	Retailers	15	10.00
	Money Lenders	02	01.33

Source : Primary Data.

Problems on Marketing of Fishes

All kinds of business activities are not free from problems; the fishermen also faced different kinds of problems in the marketing of fish. To examine the problems of marketing, factor analysis has been utilized by the researcher. The study clearly reveals the lack of marketing knowledge of fishermen which is an important factor. The factor analysis reveals the high factor loading, indicating the major problems in the marketing of fish followed by natural calamities, lack of Government support, competition, and exploitation of fishermen by middlemen. Table-9 discloses the fact.

Table-9 : Problems on Marketing of Fishes

S.No.	Marketing Problems	Rotated Factor Loading Value			
		Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4
1.	Lack of marketing knowledge of fishermen	.832	-.033	-.040	-.048
2.	Inadequate storage facility	.622	-.243	.447	.173
3.	Insufficient expertise in fish grading and processing	.607	-.078	.187	-.224
4.	Lack of organized market activities	.422	.257	.321	-.375
5.	Natural calamities	-.216	.761	-.071	.051
6.	Lack of government support	.571	.547	.255	.083
7.	Raining problems	-.480	.505	.271	.063
8.	Competition	-.353	.120	.722	-.068
9.	Wide price variations	.184	-.068	.691	.402
10.	Insufficient facilities for cleaning at the market premises	-.229	.089	.604	-.010
11.	Exploitation of fishermen by middlemen	.531	.184	.336	-.553

Source : Computed data.

Borrowing Capacity

Every business or trade thrives on borrowing money. In the present study, the investigator has endeavored to examine the borrowing capability of the respondents. The analysis indicates that a notable portion (82 percent) of the respondents have borrowed money from Money lenders, banks, and Cooperative societies to meet their fishing expenses like buying craft, engines and settling an old debt. The results are shown in Table-10.

Table-10 : Borrowings of the Respondents

Borrowings of the Respondents		No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Capacity of Borrowing	Yes	123	82.00
	No	27	18.00
Source of Borrowings	Commercial Banks	06	4.88
	Co-operative Societies	07	5.70
	Private Banks	29	23.58
	Money Lenders	56	45.52
	Friends and Relatives	25	20.32
Purpose of Borrowings	To buy a craft	20	13.33
	To buy a gear	10	6.67
	To buy an engine	20	13.33
	To meet the fishing expenses	55	36.67
	To meet personal expenses	08	5.33
	To settle old debts	10	6.67
Mode of Repayment	By single payment	23	18.70
	Daily	18	14.64
	Weekly	16	13.00
	Monthly installment	61	49.60
	Once in six months	03	2.44
	Once a year	02	1.62

Source : Computed data.

Awareness of Welfare Schemes Offered by the Government

Both the Central and State Government offers welfare schemes for the upliftment of fishermen in India particularly in Tamil Nadu. To examine the awareness of welfare schemes among the respondents, it indicates that only 22.67 percent of them are aware of welfare schemes of the Government. Both the vacation period

(54.12 percent) and storm period (45.88 percent), and the fishermen have received compensation from the Government as Rs. 2,000-5,000 and 93.75 percent of the respondents were availed of tsunami relief homes. Table-11 discloses the fact.

Table-11 : Awareness of Welfare Schemes

Awareness of Welfare Schemes		No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Awareness of welfare schemes	Yes	34	22.67
	No	116	77.33
Compensation received	Vacation period	59	54.12
	Storm period	50	45.88
Amount of compensation	Below Rs. 2000	60	55.05
	Rs.2000 - Rs.5000	40	36.70
	Above Rs.5000	09	8.25
Tsunami relief homes availed	Yes	90	93.75
	No	06	6.25

Source : Computed data.

Expectation of Benefits from the Government

To examine the expectation of benefits from the Government, the researcher has applied Garret's ranking method. It clearly reveals that Storage facilities, Educational facilities, Transport facilities and protection from other nation's guards are the major benefits expected by the respondents. Table-12 discloses the fact.

Table-12 : Mean Score for Expectation of Benefits from the Government

S.No.	Benefits	Total Score	Mean Score	Rank
1	Storage facilities	829	5.52	I
2	Educational facilities	773	5.15	II
3	Transport facilities	746	4.97	III
4	Protection from other nation's guards	692	4.61	IV
5	Medical facilities	671	4.47	V
6	Housing facilities	662	4.41	VI
7	Credit facilities	513	3.42	VII
8	Insurance facilities	507	3.38	VIII

Source : Computed data.

Factors Influencing the Level of Satisfaction Towards Occupation

To understand the overall satisfaction of the respondents towards their occupation, Factor analysis has been used by the researcher. The study

unequivocally shows that among the several attitude scales, availability of bank loans and advances and Government regulations are the important factors that influence the level of satisfaction of the fishermen, followed by a second factor as maintenance of boats for fishing, third-factor high factor loading is the marketing of fishes, insurance coverage to the equipment and to the fishermen influence the level of satisfaction of the fishermen. The results are shown in Table-13.

Table-13 : Factors Influencing the Level of Satisfaction

S.No.	Variables	Rotated Factor Loading Value			
		Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4
1.	Availability of bank loans and advances	1.129	.211	.057	.044
2.	Government regulations	1.026	.104	.192	.086
3.	Fishing activities	.455	1.287	-.010	-.151
4.	Maintenance boats for fishing	-.012	1.023	.169	.143
5.	Marketing of fishes	.072	-.082	1.024	-.078
6.	Insurance coverage to the equipment	.095	.124	.735	-.324
7.	Insurance coverage to the fishermen	.106	.451	.619	.165
8.	Improvement in the standard of living	-.164	.180	-.102	1.165
9.	Political intervention in fishing societies	.377	-.082	-.141	.797

Source : Computed data.

Findings

- Most of the 30-40 year-old marine fishermen (71.33 percent) are illiterate and remaining are only completed elementary school, married into a nuclear family with more than four members belonging to the religion of Hindu, Muslim and Christian have actively involved in fishing.
- According to the survey's occupation, out of 150 respondents, 70% had started fishing when they were 13 to 17 years old, going out to sea 200–250 days a year in used country boats. They actively participated in boat repairs, fish vending, and training new aspirants. The respondents' spouses also engaged in fish vending and fish processing to provide income for the family, but they also faced challenges with fish scarcity and high boat maintenance costs.
- Economic conditions reveal that income of respondents falls between Rs.10000- 15000, which is sufficient only for their basic needs and they are able to save meagre amount of savings for future contingencies.

- The lifestyle of fishermen indicates that most of the respondents (80 percent) have owned house as hut, concrete and tiled and able to get stable food with consumption habits of smoking, liquoring and pan masala.
- Majority of the respondents are forced to sell their products to wholesalers at cheaper rate and the factor analysis on problems on marketing of fishes reveals that lack of marketing knowledge, natural calamities etc., and they expect the storage facilities from the Government.
- Availability of bank loans& advances, government regulations on fishing activities, maintenance of boats and marketing are the important factors which influences the level of satisfaction of the respondents towards their occupation.

Suggestions

In order to enhance the present level of socio-economic conditions of marine fishermen of Rameswaram in Ramanathapuram District, the researcher suggests the following based on the findings;

- The literacy level of the fishermen is very low. Further, they do not have adequate technical knowledge to operate and carrying out repair works of the mechanised boats. Hence, the Government can encourage the nearby government and private engineering college to provide hands on training to the fishermen on the working and service of mechanised boats during their vacation period, as part of their extension programme at free of cost.
- The study reveals that the major problem faced by the fishermen in marketing of fish is lack of marketing knowledge. Hence, the government through its social welfare department can organize programmes to give them adequate marketing knowledge.
- Fish is a perishable commodity; the fishermen are forced to sell fishes to the middlemen at cheaper rate. Hence, it is suggested that the government can construct cold storage facilities and provide the facility to the fishermen at nominal rent.
- The lead bank of Ramanathapuram District may provide loan to the fishermen to construct their own cold storage warehouses.

Conclusion

Even yet, India ranks in the top ten nations in the world for fish production. In many regions of India, the markets for marine items are disorganized. The

markets must be reformed by using new management strategies and updating the conventional fish marketing strategies. The majority of fisherman live in poverty and face numerous challenges, such as low family income, low literacy, large families combined with limited financial resources, lack of other off-season work opportunities, inadequate storage facilities, etc. The fishing community lives according to the national culture. They work in a seasonal capacity. They are not capable of doing other jobs. Because of this, they are not paid during the off-season, which presents further financial challenges.

Since this coastline is unique by nature, the majority of the fishermen use country boats (Vallam). Since they do not engage in deep sea fishing, they depend on money lenders for loans and are taken advantage of by middlemen and agents when selling their products in the Ramnad market. The central and state governments have been introducing a number of specialized schemes and projects to improve the socioeconomic conditions of the fishermen. In this context, the present study focused on those which are currently relevant to the overall upliftment of the fishermen in general and fishermen of Rameshwaram in Ramanathapuram District in particular.

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